

Heat Transfer in Unsteady Flow of Third-Grade Fluid Over a Flat Rigid Plate with Porous Medium

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Abstract

This study investigates the heat transfer characteristics of an unsteady flow of a third-grade fluid over a flat rigid plate embedded in a porous medium. The governing equations, including the momentum and energy equations, are derived based on the assumptions of incompressible fluid and negligible body forces. Analytical methods are employed to solve the coupled non-linear equations. The effects of various parameters, such as the porosity of the medium, thermal conductivity, and the non-Newtonian fluid properties, on the velocity, temperature profiles, and skin friction are discussed extensively. The results provide insights into optimizing heat transfer processes in engineering applications, including polymer processing and geothermal systems.

Keywords: Heat transfer, third-grade fluid, unsteady flow, porous medium, flat plate, boundary layer.

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Introduction

The study of non-Newtonian fluids, particularly third-grade fluids, has gained significant attention due to their relevance in industrial applications such as polymer extrusion, lubricant design, and biomedical engineering. Third-grade fluids exhibit complex rheological behaviors characterized by shear thinning or thickening, which standard Newtonian models cannot describe. In this context, understanding the heat transfer and flow characteristics of these fluids over surfaces, especially under unsteady conditions, is of practical importance.

The inclusion of a porous medium further complicates the flow dynamics, as it introduces additional resistance and affects heat dissipation. Researchers have extensively studied porous media flows due to their applications in geothermal energy, filtration systems, and enhanced oil recovery. This study aims to analyze the heat transfer characteristics of third-grade fluids flowing over a flat rigid plate embedded in a porous medium under unsteady conditions.

Some important contributions include the work of Sajid et al., (2008), Domairry et al. (2009),

Hayat et al., (2010), Chen et al., (2011). The flow characteristics of non-Newtonian fluids differ significantly from those of Newtonian fluids. Consequently, in practical applications, the behavior of non-Newtonian fluids cannot be substituted with that of Newtonian fluids. It is crucial to analyze and understand their flow dynamics to enhance their application across various industries.

Ali et al. (2023) examined the MHD stagnation-point flow of a third-grade fluid over a porous stretching sheet with thermal radiation effects. Their study revealed that increasing the Hartmann number boosts the velocity profile, while higher radiation parameters enhance temperature distribution. They used a hybrid algorithm combining finite difference and shooting methods for solving the governing equations. Similarly, Sahoo (2022) analyzed heat transfer in MHD stagnation-point flow over a porous sheet and found that thermal radiation significantly increases temperature distribution, whereas the porous parameter reduces velocity near the sheet.

Khan et al. (2023) explored heat and mass transfer in third-grade fluid flow over an inclined elongating sheet, factoring in magnetic fields and chemical reactions. Their findings showed that the magnetic field suppresses velocity, and chemical reactions reduce concentration distribution, emphasizing the relevance to industrial applications involving inclined surfaces and magnetic fields. In another study, Khan et al. (2022) numerically investigated hydromagnetic third-grade fluid flow through a porous medium with temperature-dependent properties. They reported that increasing porous permeability stabilizes flow, elevates velocity and temperature, and promotes entropy generation. Conversely, increased temperature-dependent electrical conductivity destabilizes the flow.

Ali et al. (2022) analyzed unsteady boundary layer flow over an oscillatory stretching sheet with thermal radiation and heat source/sink effects. They demonstrated that higher thermal radiation enhances temperature profiles, while increased heat sources lead to thicker thermal boundary layers. Siddique et al. (2020) focused on entropy optimization in third-grade nanofluid

slip flow over a stretchable sheet. They found that higher slip parameters reduce velocity gradients and entropy generation, whereas nanoparticle volume fractions enhance heat transfer rates.

The third-grade fluid model offers valuable insights into the physical characteristics of non-Newtonian fluids, capturing phenomena such as die-swell, the rod-climbing effect (Schowalter, 1978), shear thinning, and shear thickening—features absent in many other models.

Research on heat transfer in unsteady flows of third-grade fluids over flat rigid plates embedded in porous media is essential for several reasons. First, third-grade fluids exhibit complex non-Newtonian behaviors, such as shear-thickening and viscoelasticity, which lead to intricate fluid dynamics not captured by conventional Newtonian models. This complexity is amplified in unsteady flow conditions, where transient effects significantly influence system behavior.

Moreover, porous media are integral to many industrial processes, including filtration, insulation, and chemical reactions. The interaction between third-grade fluids and porous structures introduces additional challenges in predicting heat transfer and fluid flow, making this research critical for process optimization.

Industrial applications such as polymer extrusion, geothermal energy extraction, and cooling technologies often involve non-Newtonian fluids, requiring accurate models to improve efficiency and reduce costs. Additionally, the influence of external factors like magnetic fields, thermal radiation, and chemical reactions on heat transfer and fluid flow further emphasizes the need for in-depth study. This research aims to address the complexities of heat transfer in unsteady flows of third-grade fluids over flat rigid plates embedded in porous media. By focusing on the non-Newtonian behavior of third-grade fluids, the study seeks to develop accurate models that capture their shear-thickening and viscoelastic properties in unsteady conditions. It investigates the effects of external factors like thermal radiation, magnetic fields, and chemical reactions on heat transfer and flow behavior.

Ultimately, the research aims to improve heat transfer efficiency in industrial processes, providing valuable insights for applications involving non-Newtonian fluids, porous media, and enhanced energy transfer.

Problem Formulation

The flow of an incompressible third-grade fluid over a flat rigid plate embedded in a porous medium is governed by the continuity, momentum, and energy equations. These equations are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where u and v are the velocity components in the x and y directions, respectively.

By following the methodology of References [20, 21], the equation of motion for the unsteady flow of third-grade fluid over the rigid plate with porous medium is

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} = & \mu \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_1 \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2 \partial t} \\ & + 6\beta_3 \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} \\ & - \frac{\phi}{\kappa} \left[\frac{\mu}{3} + \alpha_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + 2\beta_3 \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] U. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In this context, U represents the velocity component, ρ denotes the fluid density, and μ is the dynamic viscosity. The parameters α_1 and β_3 are material constants, whose detailed definitions and conditions can be found in (Fosdick and Rajagopal, 1980). Additionally, ϕ corresponds to the porosity, and κ represents the permeability of the porous medium.

In order to solve (1) mentioned above, boundary conditions are specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} U(0, t) &= U_0 V(t), & t > 0, & \quad (a) \\ U(\infty, t) &= 0, & t > 0, & \quad (b) \\ U(y, 0) &= 0, & y > 0, & \quad (c) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where U_0 is the reference velocity. The first boundary condition (2a) is the no-slip condition and the second boundary condition (2b) says that the main stream velocity is zero. This is not a restrictive assumption since we can always measure velocity relative to the main stream. The initial condition (2c) indicates that the fluid is initially at rest.

Energy Equation

The Temperature equation, which involve heat generation or absorption for the flow is also given as

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + Q(T - T_\infty) \quad (3)$$

where all parameters have their usual meanings. The appropriate initial and boundary conditions for this purpose are:

$$\begin{aligned} t \leq 0: & \quad T = T_w + A \left(\frac{x}{L} \right)^2 \quad \forall y \\ t > 0: & \quad \begin{cases} -k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = h(T_w - T) & y = 0 \\ T \rightarrow T_\infty, & \text{as } y \rightarrow \infty \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where A is a positive parameter.

Assuming that material properties appearing in the above equation are constant, the momentum equation can be solved regardless of the energy equation.

On introducing the nondimensional quantities

$$\begin{aligned} U' &= \frac{U}{U_0}, y' = \frac{U_0 y}{\nu}, t' = \frac{U_0^2 t}{\nu}, \alpha' = \frac{\alpha_1 U_0^2}{\rho \nu^2}, \\ \frac{1}{K} &= \frac{\phi \nu^2}{\kappa U_0^2}, \beta' = \frac{2\beta_3 U_0^4}{\rho \nu^2}, \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty} = \theta(t, y) \end{aligned}$$

Equations (1) and (3) and the corresponding initial and the boundary conditions (2) and (4) take the form

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} = \mu_* \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_* \frac{\partial^3 U}{\partial y^2 \partial t} + 3\gamma \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y}\right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} - \gamma_* U \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{3K_*} U \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + \lambda \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \delta \theta \quad (6)$$

$$t \geq 0: \begin{cases} U(0, t) = V(t), \\ \frac{\partial \theta(0, t)}{\partial y} = B_i(\theta(0, t) - 1) \\ U(y, t) \rightarrow 0, \\ \theta(0, t) \rightarrow 0, \end{cases} \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty \quad (7)$$

$$t \leq 0: U(y, 0) = 0, \theta(y, 0) = 1, y > 0.$$

where

$$\mu_* = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\alpha}{K}}, \alpha_* = \frac{\alpha}{1 + \frac{\alpha}{K}}, \gamma = \frac{\beta}{1 + \frac{\alpha}{K}},$$

$$\gamma_* = \frac{\frac{\beta}{K}}{1 + \frac{\alpha}{K}}, \frac{1}{K_*} = \frac{1}{K}, Pr = \frac{\mu C_p}{\kappa_\tau},$$

$$\lambda = \frac{U_0^2}{C_p(T_w - T_\infty)}, \delta = \frac{Qv^2}{U_0 \mu C_p}.$$

Method of Solution

This work emphasizes deriving closed-form solutions for boundary value problems associated with nonlinear diffusion equations governing the behavior of non-Newtonian third-grade fluids in porous media. The solutions are constructed using the Lie group method for differential equations, and numerical simulations are provided to illustrate the influence of physical parameters on flow properties.

Group-invariant Solutions

This method uses invariants of a group G to reformulate the differential equation in terms of these, which will result in an equation with one less independent variable. In our current study, we have a PDE $F(t, y, U^2) = 0$ in two independent variables t and y with a symmetry generated by

$$X = \xi(t, y, U) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \tau(t, y, U) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + \eta(t, y, U) \frac{\partial}{\partial U} \quad (8)$$

with corresponding characteristic equations

$$\frac{dt}{\xi} = \frac{dy}{\tau} = \frac{dU}{\eta}. \quad (9)$$

We get two invariants $r(t, y, U)$ and $s(t, y, U)$ (in general one less than the number of variables Fosdick and K. R. Rajagopal (1980)). Letting one play the role of dependent variable, $s = f(r)$, we determine the derivatives of U in terms of s with respect to r (and perhaps y or t which will later be redundant). We observed that (5) is independent of t explicitly, so it is invariant under the Lie point symmetry generator X . Thus by (9) corresponding characteristic equations is

$$\frac{dt}{1} = \frac{dy}{0} = \frac{dU}{0} = 0, \quad (10)$$

implying the steady-state solution given by

$$U = f(\eta), \theta = g(\eta) \quad \text{where } \eta = y. \quad (11)$$

Substituting (11) into (5) and (6) yields ODE's, which we solve to find the solutions that are invariant under the given group action as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_* \frac{d^2 f}{d\eta^2} + 3\gamma \left(\frac{df}{d\eta}\right)^2 \frac{d^2 f}{d\eta^2} \\ - \gamma_* f \left(\frac{df}{d\eta}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{3K_*} f = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \eta^2} + \lambda \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta}\right)^2 + \delta g(\eta) = 0. \quad (13)$$

with the transformed boundary conditions (7) become

$$\begin{aligned} f(0,) = a_1, -\frac{\partial g(0)}{\partial \eta} = Bi(1 - g(0)) \\ f(\eta) \rightarrow 0, \theta(\eta) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We have now transformed the governing nonlinear PDE (5) and (6) into a nonlinear ODE (12) and (13) as well as the boundary conditions (6) to the boundary conditions (14).

Now, to obtain an analytical solution to (12) and (13) subject to (14), we first solve (13) for $f(\eta)$, since it is independent of $g(\eta)$.

Following the work of Fosdick and K. R. Rajagopal (1980) and Aziz and Mahomed (2014), we assume a solution of the form

$$f(\eta) = a_2 \exp(a_3 \eta), \quad (15)$$

where a_2 and a_3 are the constants to be determined. We then substituting (15) into (12), and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_* a_3^2 - \frac{1}{K_*} + \\ + e^{2a_3 \eta} (3\gamma a_2^2 a_3^4 - \gamma_* a_2^2 a_3^2) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

If we decomposed (16) in the powers of e^0 and $e^{2a_3 \eta}$, we obtain that

$$e^0: \mu_* a_3^2 - \frac{1}{3K_*} = 0, \quad (17)$$

$$e^{2a_3 \eta}: 3\gamma a_2^2 a_3^4 - \gamma_* a_2^2 a_3^2 = 0. \quad (18)$$

Equation (18) implies

$$a_3 = \pm \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma}}. \quad (19)$$

For our assumed solution to satisfy the condition at infinity, we choose

$$a_3 = -\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma}}, \quad (20)$$

But equations (17) and (18) must be identically satisfied, to ensure this, we substitute the value of a_3 obtained from (18) into (17), thus we have

$$\mu_* \frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma} - \frac{1}{K_*} = 0, \quad (21)$$

Hence, we write (15), the solution for $f(\eta)$ explicitly as

$$U = f(\eta) = a_1 \exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma}} \eta\right), \quad (22)$$

provided that condition of (21) holds.

Now, substituting (22) into (13), we have

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \eta^2} + Pr \delta g(\eta) = Pr \lambda \left(a_1 \exp \left(-\eta \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma}} \right) \right)^2. \quad (23)$$

The solution to (23) is obtained through complementary and particular solutions using method of undetermined coefficients. We have

$$g(\eta) = \frac{\left(\frac{Bi(Pr a_1^2 - 4) + 2 Pr \left(a_1^2 \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma}} + Bi \delta \sqrt{\frac{3\gamma}{\gamma_*}} \right)}{2 \left(2 - Pr \delta \sqrt{\frac{3\gamma}{\gamma_*}} \right) (\sqrt{Pr \delta} + Bi)} \right) e^{-\eta \sqrt{Pr \delta}}}{2 \left(2 - Pr \delta \sqrt{\frac{3\gamma}{\gamma_*}} \right) (\sqrt{Pr \delta} + Bi)} + \frac{Pr a_1^2}{2 \left(Pr \delta \sqrt{\frac{3\gamma}{\gamma_*}} - 2 \right)} \exp \left(-2\eta \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_*}{3\gamma}} \right) \quad (24)$$

where $a_1, \delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$,

Analysis and Discussion

To proceed with the analysis of the behaviour and properties of the essential physical parameters governing the flow, we choose the base values of the parameters as $\gamma = 0.5, \gamma_* = 0.75, \mu_1 = 1.5$, and $K_1 = \alpha_1 = 1$, and $l_1 = l_2 = l_3 = 1$ and the plot are shown in Figures 1–14.

Impact of Parameters on Flow Velocity and Temperature Distributions

The influence of various dimensionless parameters on the flow velocity and temperature fields in the unsteady flow of a third-grade fluid over a flat rigid plate with a porous medium is analyzed as follows:

The modified viscoelastic term (α_1), reflects the viscoelastic effects of the fluid. An increase in α_1 heightens fluid elasticity, potentially thickening the velocity boundary layer and lowering peak velocity (Figure 1). In temperature fields, Figure 2, this reduced fluid motion results in a thicker thermal boundary layer due to lower convective heat transfer.

The modified material constant (γ), captures nonlinear shear thickening or shear-thinning

behavior. A higher γ enhances localized velocity peaks due to shear effects but may destabilize the flow when excessive as represented in Figure 3. Additionally, in Figure 4, the increased viscous dissipation from larger γ values steepens the temperature gradient, enhancing heat transfer near the plate. The **dimensionless term** (γ_1), combines the effects of non-Newtonian behavior and porous medium resistance (Figure 5). Higher γ_1 suppresses the velocity profile by increasing flow resistance, while its impact on temperature fields includes reduced convective heat transfer and a thicker thermal boundary layer as displayed in Figure 6.

The dimensionless heat generation term (δ), accounts for internal heat generation or absorption. Positive heat generation ($Q > 0$) raises fluid temperatures, decreasing viscosity and increasing velocity. Conversely, heat absorption ($Q < 0$) increases viscosity, slowing the fluid motion while, heat generation thickens the thermal boundary layer, while heat absorption reduces its thickness Figure 7.

Whereas, the Biot number (Bi), represents the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer. Higher Bi values enhance heat transfer at the surface, indirectly increasing velocity by reducing viscosity. A higher Bi results in steeper gradients near the plate Figure 8, while lower Bi values correspond to conduction dominated heat transfer and a more uniform temperature profile.

Table 1. Summary of Impacts

Parameter	Velocity Field	Temperature Field
δ	Heat generation accelerates flow; heat absorption reduces it.	Increases or decreases thermal boundary layer thickness.
α^*	Increases flow elasticity, potentially reducing peak velocity.	Reduces convective heat transfer, thickening the boundary layer.
γ	Amplifies nonlinear shear effects, enhancing velocity peaks.	Generates additional heat, steepening the temperature gradient.
γ^*	Increases resistance to flow,	Reduces convective heat transfer, thickening the

	suppressing velocity.	thermal boundary layer.
Bi	Indirectly enhances flow through increased heat transfer.	Steeper temperature gradients near the plate.

Effect of Parameters on Skin Friction and Nusselt Number

The parameters under consideration—dimensionless term (γ_1), modified material constant (γ), dimensionless heat generation term (δ), and Biot number (Bi)—significantly influence the skin friction and Nusselt number in the context of heat transfer in unsteady flow of third-grade fluid over a flat plate. Their effects are discussed below:

Effect on Skin Friction

The parameter γ_1 , Figure 8, which combines effects of material properties and porous medium resistance, introduces additional flow resistance. An increase in γ_1 leads to higher shear stress at the wall, thereby increasing the skin friction coefficient. This occurs because the additional resistance from the porous medium dampens fluid motion near the wall. The parameter γ accounts for nonlinear effects such as shear-thinning or shear-thickening behavior of the fluid, Figure 10. An increase in γ enhances the shear effects near the wall, increasing the skin friction coefficient. However, excessively high γ values may destabilize the flow, potentially leading to oscillatory shear stresses. For positive δ (heat generation), the fluid temperature rises, reducing viscosity near the plate. This lowers the shear stress and decreases the skin friction coefficient. Conversely, for negative δ (heat absorption), increased viscosity enhances shear stress, increasing the skin friction coefficient. The Biot number primarily influences heat transfer at the surface rather than directly affecting skin friction. However, higher Bi values, which enhance heat dissipation at the surface, can indirectly reduce viscosity near the plate and slightly lower the skin friction coefficient.

Effect on Nusselt Number

In Figure 11, Higher γ_1 values suppress fluid motion, reducing convective heat transfer near the surface. This results in a decrease in the Nusselt number, indicating a lower rate of heat transfer at the surface.

As γ increases, viscous dissipation generates additional heat near the plate, Figure 12. This results in a steeper temperature gradient at the surface, increasing the Nusselt number and thus enhancing heat transfer. Positive δ (heat generation) increases the thermal boundary layer thickness but steepens the temperature gradient near the plate, resulting in a higher Nusselt number. For negative δ (heat absorption), the opposite occurs, with a reduced Nusselt number due to lower thermal activity, Figure 13. A higher Bi increases the efficiency of convective heat transfer from the surface to the surrounding fluid. This leads to a steeper temperature gradient at the wall, significantly enhancing the Nusselt number. Lower Bi values, corresponding to conduction-dominated heat transfer Figure 14, reduce the Nusselt number.

Table 2. Effects of Parameters on Skin Friction and Nusselt Number

Parameter	Effect on Skin Friction	Effect on Nusselt Number
γ_1	Increases due to additional resistance from the porous medium.	Decreases as suppressed fluid motion reduces convective heat transfer.
γ	Increases due to enhanced shear effects; may destabilize flow at high values.	Increases due to viscous dissipation steepening the temperature gradient.
δ	Decreases for heat generation; increases for heat absorption.	Increases for heat generation; decreases for heat absorption.
Bi	Slight decrease due to viscosity reduction at higher Bi .	Increases significantly with enhanced surface heat transfer.

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of heat transfer in unsteady flow of a third-grade fluid over a flat rigid plate embedded in a porous medium. The findings emphasize the interplay between non-Newtonian fluid properties, porous medium characteristics, and thermal effects, offering valuable insights for optimizing industrial processes involving complex fluids.

The analysis highlights the significant influence of parameters such as the heat generation term (δ), and material constants (γ, γ_1) on the flow velocity, temperature fields, skin friction, and

Nusselt number. These parameters collectively determine the nature of heat transfer and momentum transport within the boundary layer, allowing precise control over system performance. The study also underscores the role of the Biot number (B_i) in regulating surface heat transfer, emphasizing its importance in applications requiring efficient thermal management. A key observation is the nonlinear relationship between these parameters and the resulting flow behavior. For instance, increased viscoelastic effects (α_1) can dampen the velocity field while thickening the thermal boundary

Figure 1. Velocity Distribution against Modified Viscoelastic Term (α_1)

Figure 2. Effect Modified Viscoelastic Term on Temperature Distribution for α_1

Figure 3. Velocity Distribution for Modified Material Constant (γ)

Figure 4. Effect Modified Material Constant on Temperature Distribution for γ

Figure 5. Velocity Distribution against Modified Dimensional Term γ_1

layer, demonstrating the trade-off between fluid elasticity and thermal efficiency. Similarly, the interplay between γ_1 and porous medium resistance provides a means to tailor flow resistance and heat transfer rates, catering to specific industrial requirements.

Key Observations

1. Increasing λ significantly enhances the temperature gradient, which indirectly accelerates the fluid near the plate due to viscosity reduction.

Figure 6. Effect Dimensionless Term on Temperature Distribution for γ_1

Figure 7. Effect Dimensionless Heat Generation Term on Temperature Distribution for γ

Figure 14. Nusselt Distribution for Dimensionless Heat Generation Term (δ)

2. Positive δ values (heat generation) accelerate the flow and increase the thermal boundary layer thickness, whereas negative δ (heat absorption) has the opposite effect.

3. Higher μ^* reduces resistance in the flow, enhancing velocity and steepening the temperature gradient through increased convective heat transfer.

4. Larger a^* thickens the velocity boundary layer due to enhanced viscoelastic effects and reduces convective heat transfer, leading to a thicker thermal boundary layer.

5. Elevated γ values amplify shear effects, creating localized velocity peaks and steepening the temperature gradient due to additional viscous dissipation.

6. A higher Biot number enhances surface heat transfer, steepens the temperature gradient, and indirectly influences flow velocity by reducing fluid viscosity near the plate.

The study's findings are particularly relevant for engineering applications such as enhanced oil recovery, polymer processing, and thermal insulation systems. By adjusting material properties and flow conditions, designers can achieve optimal heat and momentum transfer while minimizing energy consumption. Furthermore, the insights into viscous dissipation and shear effects contribute to

understanding energy loss mechanisms in non-Newtonian flows.

Conflict of Interests

No conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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